

Clean information and communication

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The growth of misinformation, the difficulty of keeping the media in operation or the consolidation of paywalls against influencers and digital platforms, places society before the urgency of guaranteeing the right to freedom of expression.

Several nations are issuing regulations to curb the circulation of lies, counteract fake videos and give citizens the tools to base their decisions on reality. In addition, there are regional initiatives being implemented by NGOs and journalists' associations, but the contamination of information continues.

In dialogues between researchers, media managers and those concerned with governance, options are discussed to enable information to continue to serve as a beacon for communities. There is talk of cultural vouchers, subsidies, standards and adopting best practices from other sciences, such as ecology, to create targeted taxes on individuals and companies that pollute, that generate externalities with the use of data mining, for example.

Low sensitivity, minimal training in media competence and selfishness influence the publications that people make through social networks. There is a need for professionals to contrast, evaluate, include voices and diversity in the news to expose plurality, and encourage many to participate in shaping public opinion. To achieve this, these dynamics must be sustained with advertising or with the mechanisms mentioned above, under transparent allocation processes.

At the heart of this is the nature of human beings, their innate right to communicate. To interrupt the means of receiving information and opinions, or expressing them, is to undo centuries of history.